

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE AVAILABILITY OF QUALIFIED TEACHERS AND LABORATORY FACILITIES FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF COMPUTER STUDIES IN SOME SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SOKOTO SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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Abstract

Computers are considered as revolutionary tools that are used in all human endeavours. However, although students were taught computer in their various schools most of them cannot identify computer physically. The net result is the poor performance in the subject. The study assessed the Availability of Qualified Teachers and Laboratory Facilities for Effective Teaching and Learning of Computer Studies in Secondary School in Sokoto South Local Government Area of Sokoto State. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population for the study comprised all public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area of Sokoto State. 10 schools were selected across the public schools using a purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using validated instrument titled Computer Laboratory Inventory (CLI) with reliable index of 0.78, and the results were analyzed using the SPSS Statistical package. Finding showed that the number of working computers is high in most of the schools laboratory for effective teaching/learning, but most of the computer teachers are not qualified even though the teacher student ratio is high compared to the criteria provided by the National Policy on Education (NPC). Based on the findings the following recommendations were made: Government should employ and post enough qualified teachers in computer studies to different secondary school, especially in Sokoto South Local Government Area; Government should provide computer laboratory to the secondary schools; and the laboratories should be well equipped with facilities.

Keyword: Computer studies, qualified teachers, laboratory facilities, teaching and learning

Introduction

The computer is regarded as a revolutionary invention of the 20th century; it revolutionized the social, technological, political and economic

spheres of the modern world. Computer has been used successfully in medicine, banking, science, space exploration, etc. It has found applications in instructional delivery, educational administration and

management. The field of computer has completely broader terms, which terms include computer education, computer awareness, computer literacy, computer assisted instruction, computer studies, etc. (Onya & Onya, 2010). Computer is considered as a very important tool for teaching and learning of different subjects and computer science in particular. This is because literature indicates that computer as an instrument used in teaching makes teaching and learning processes more enjoyable, interesting and interactive learning outcomes, especially, when educational software, games, PowerPoint presentation, visual presentation etc are used (Aduwa & Iyamu, 2005).

Furthermore, there is an expanded benefit of using computer in teaching and learning process as it promotes great collaboration among students, gives rapid & accurate feedback, and contributes towards positive motivation in learning different subjects (Becta, 2003; Iji & Udan 2007, Pilli, 2013). Iji & Udam, (2007) specifically indicated that computer when used in teaching and learning, encouraged students to have a good problem-solving skill in mathematics. Aduwa & Iyamu (2005), explained that, computer skills develop students' generic problem solving or thinking skills and serves as agent of socialization. However, as indicated by

Aduwa and Iyamu (2005) adequate facilities are very crucial in teaching and learning of computer science as they enable the teacher and the learner to carry out their roles. These facilities include the text books, classrooms instructional materials, ICT gadgets, libraries and laboratories facilities etc. One importance of using computer in learning is to give students the opportunity to manipulate and experiment with suitable equipment and materials, and prepare their computer skills in order to address global challenges.

A computer laboratory can be described as a safe place where students and teacher carryout computer oriented activities. It provides a room for teaching computer with appropriate equipment. In carrying out scientific work and research in the laboratory certain facilities are required such as; computer systems, which are the working computers with all the required hardware and software components; Computer Input and output devices including Printers, Projectors, Scanners, Cameras, etc; Electricity; Internet service; and ICT gadgets. (Yusuf, 2005). Literature indicated that, generally, computer is an important tool in the teaching and learning of different subjects and computer science in particular, because computer as instrument used in teaching makes teaching and learning process more

enjoyable, interesting and interactive by using software programs such as educational games, PowerPoint presentation and other visual presentation and ICT gadgets such as projector, interactive board, and television. (Aduwa & Iyamu, 2005)

In view of the benefit/importance of computer for national development, Nigeria made computer education one of the vocational subjects in upper basic education, senior secondary and in tertiary institution; this was aimed at preparing younger generation to address global challenges (National Policy on Education (NPE), 2004). It was observed by Hedberg (2003) that often times teachers of computer sciences mostly emphasize cognitive domain at the expense of the other two affective and psychomotor domains which provide adequate exposition of students to practical activities in computer science. For effective teaching and learning of computer science in both primary and secondary institutions, there must be a well-equipped computer laboratory capable of giving students adequate computer experience practical and demonstration exposure. This is more so that teaching and learning of computer, as stated in the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2004), “should be by practical, explanatory and experimental method”. The qualification of teachers

therefore is paramount. No matter how wonderful a curriculum is, its efficiency and effectiveness depends on the quality/qualification of the teachers. It is against this background that the researchers intend to find out the availability of teachers and laboratory facilities for effective teaching and learning of computer science in junior secondary school in Sokoto metropolis.

Literature Review

A computer is referred to a device that accepts information (in the form of digitalized data) and manipulates it for some result based on a program or sequence of instructions on how the data is to be processed. Computer can also be referred to as an electronic device manufactured to accept an ordered sequence of instructions given to it in appropriate language and to carry out these instructions with great speed and accuracy. In the earliest time, computer was known as abacus used in the Middle East as a tool for computation, which was developed between 2700 – 2300BC. The earlier computer used vacuum tubes, followed by transistor, integrated circuit and finally microchips (NTI, 1990).

A teacher (also called a school teacher or, in some contexts, an educator) is a person who helps others to acquire knowledge, competences or values. Qualified teachers are those teachers who

meet the requirements of the educational board or governing body, i.e National Policy on Education (NPC). For a teacher to qualified, he or she is usually required to obtain a Bachelor or graduate degree in Education, degree in any other field of study plus education or minimum qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), (NPE, 2013). Also, the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN, 2012), specifically required that the qualified teachers categorized from Ph.D. Masters, Bachelors/HND in other field of study must have additional educational certificate or minimum of NCE before they can teach.

Availability of Computer Teachers

Teachers are the pillar by which the standard of education in any country of the world can be measured. The higher the level/quality of teachers the higher the quality of education and vice versa. It is on this that the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2013:5) reiterated that “Government shall make provision in teachers’ education for specialization in early childhood care and education, and retention of teachers”. This statement captures the major concern at this level of education, which is the need to have qualified teachers in sufficient numbers who have enough interest and job satisfaction to be able to bring about the required readiness for learning in children

at this foundation level of lifelong learning. Mkpa (1997) had opined that the concept of qualified teacher goes in random with having adequate teaching facilities such as pictures and charts needed to draw attention of students precisely to the aspects of the learning required by the Accompanying teaching with visual illustration make it clearer and more learnable and interesting. Thus, Ifejika (1990) had also suggested that the teaching of science and technical subject requires the use of specialized teachers as well as specialized laboratory tools and facilities as these enhance the students’ exposure to practicals.

Teacher’s effectiveness in a subject as a prime determinant of student’s performance in the subject is highly important. Ineffective teaching in our junior secondary school system is from the quality of teachers being recruited to teach science especially computer science. In most of our schools, computer science is taught by people who are neither interested nor qualified to lead operate the available equipment. Some of the teacher have little or no basic knowledge of computer laboratory facilities. How then can they utilize them?

Science Laboratory in Nigerian Schools
Researchers have found science laboratories to be central to the teaching of science in secondary schools

(Adeyemi, 1998). Laboratories have been found to be the scientists' workshops where practical activities are conducted to enhance a meaningful learning of science concepts and theories (Seweje, 2000; Olubor and Unyimadu, 2001). They have also been found to be a primary vehicle for promoting formal reasoning skills and students' understanding, thereby enhancing desired learning outcomes in students (Jeske, 1990; Ogunleye, 2002).

Jones (1990) examined teacher provision in the sciences in many countries and found that 45% of the schools surveyed indicated insufficient laboratories. His findings agreed with Barrow's (1991) findings in Saudi Arabia which indicated inadequacy in the provision of laboratory facilities in schools. The findings were also consistent with those of Black (1998), who found in Uganda that science education is faced with the problem of lack of resources with half the schools having no real laboratory.

The availabilities of teachers and laboratory facilities of computer science contribute enormously for effective learning and teaching of computer science.

According to Shamsudeen & Nasiru (2016), science as a study of nature can best be understood when taught practically. That is, it is easy to

understand and assimilate science when it is practically oriented. Alebiosu (2004) stated that science is experimentation and its teaching especially focuses on making students learn through the working of hands, brain, and the heart. The laboratory is central to meaningful and effective learning of any of the science. It refers to any equipped building or place where scientists do their works. Ciroma & Bakori (2010) defined laboratory as a place where meaningful learning of science can be practiced by verifying scientific principles, theories or laws. The use of laboratory equipment may, in fact, be regarded as complex activities that include planning, organization and coordination of equipment and activities in the laboratory in a manner conducive for scientific investigation. (Shamsudeen & Nasiru, 2016).

Laboratory facilities are important in teaching and learning computer science as well as being powerful interest arousing devices such as information and communication technology devices that bring into play the sense of touch, sight, and sound. However it is the responsibility of teacher to bring the laboratory to life through the effective use of the laboratory facilities in our schools. (Pearce, 2014).

Notwithstanding, researchers have found shortages in the number of laboratories in Nigerian schools

(Alebiosu, 2000; Onipede, 2003). They argued that many schools do not have required laboratory facilities. Hence, students often fail to acquire science laboratory skills because their teachers were unable to conduct practical as they would like to and this always had inevitable consequences for students' learning (Anderson, 1976). These shortages of laboratory facilities could have serious implications on the quality of schools' output. All these show the importance attached to science laboratories in schools.

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that science laboratory is a critical variable in determining the quality of output from secondary schools. The findings show that science laboratory had significant relationship with quality of output from secondary schools. Schools having laboratories in the three science subjects performed best in the examinations out of the three groups of schools with different numbers of science laboratories.

Computer Science Laboratory in Nigeria Secondary Schools

A computer laboratory is a space which provides computer services to a defined community, institution, etc. Computer laboratories are typically provided by libraries to the public, by academic institutions to students who attend the institution, or by other institutions to the

public or to people affiliated with that institution. Computers in computer laboratories are typically equipped with internet access, while scanners and printers may augment the laboratory setup. Computers in computer labs are typically arranged either in rows, so that every workstation has a similar view of one end of the room to facilitate lecturing or presentations, or in clusters, to facilitate small group work. (Blink & Claire, 2015)

While computer laboratories are generally multipurpose, some laboratories may contain computers with hardware or software optimized for certain tasks or processes, depending on the needs of the institution/school operating the laboratory. These specialized purposes include but may not be limited to video editing, stock trading, 3-D design, and programming. (Hawkins, Brian, Oblinger, & Diana, 2015)

Computer/ICT education was introduced in the nation's educational curriculum due to its relevance in education in this contemporary era; Ajayi (2002) pointed out that any country that neglected computer/ICT has already deleted her progress from the modern era development no matter how wealthy such country is. Though the importance of ICT/computer science laboratory in the educational system and economic development cannot be overemphasized

and governments in Nigeria have tried to integrate computer/ICT in the educational system, the level of computer/ICT illiteracy is still on the high side. The slow pace of computer education development in Nigeria has become a source of concern. Okebukola (1997) concluded that computer is not part of classroom technology in over 90% of public schools in Nigeria. Thus, the chalkboard and textbooks continue to dominate classroom activities in most secondary schools in Nigeria.

Khalid (2009) in his research stated that teachers have strong aspiration to integrate computer/ICT education into teaching but they are impeded by many barriers like lack of competency and confidence, inadequate funds to provide a well-equipped laboratory, lack of access to resources like the hardware, software, peripherals, lack of professional development, insufficient technical support etcetera.

A recent research study by Asiyai (2014) concluded that the integration of ICT/laboratory facilities in teaching and learning of secondary schools in some State of Nigeria is low as a result of some factors like poor stake holders' attitude towards ICT policy, poor funding of ICT facilities, insufficient technical staff and others. Eze & Aja (2014) in their study of the available laboratory facilities in the secondary schools in Ebonyi Local

Government Area remarked that the facilities are being under-utilized as a result of lack of adequate trained personnel; while most of the computer ICT facilities are not in good condition for effective teaching and learning utilization. Badau and Sakiyo (2013) who carried out an investigation on teachers' competence to implement ICT/computer education curriculum in secondary schools reported low competency in the utilization of ICT/computer as a result of inadequate facilities, lack of trained teachers, insufficient power supply and government policy inconsistency.

Oshionebo and Ashang (2011) carried out a study on the ICT integration curriculum status of secondary school teachers and principals in Nigeria; it was reported that the integration of ICT is not encouraging and that the traditional way of using chalk and board still takes upper hands in Nigerian secondary schools. Efforts have been made to integrate ICT in secondary schools by making sure that there is adequate provision of computer/ICT facilities and its utilization but still many schools do not offer ICT training programmes (Goshit, 2006). Lack of ICT facilities in schools hinders teachers from using ICT to teach (Okwudishu, 2005). Most previous studies reported that continual power failure in Nigeria has formed a major differently in the integration and

implementation of computer/ICT in the educational system (Okebukola 1998; Egunjobi, 2003; Asiyai, 2014).

Onojetah (2012) complained that poor ICT infrastructural facilities, insufficient funding, lack of manpower, poor internet connectivity and non-provision of good computer/ICT laboratories brought about poor integration and implementation of ICT in the educational system in Nigeria. The study carried out by Aduwa-Ogiegbaen & Iyamu (2005) concluded that inadequacy of fund, power supply, relevant text books and trained computer have been drawing ICT backwards. Without computer/ICT, economic and technological development in this 21st century will elude Nigeria (Aduwa-Ogiegbaen & Iyamu, 2005).

Aniebonam (2008) reported that lack of computer facilities and incompetent teachers have created a very wide gap in the effort to bridge digital divide in Nigerian academic empowerment. It is understood that many secondary schools in Nigeria teach computer/ICT courses to their students starting from the junior class, yet the level of computer illiteracy is still high. Some primary schools in urban areas also have computer/ICT outfits in order to make the pupils computer literate, but the outcome of these efforts continue to result to high computer/ICT illiteracy

among the students. It is clear that they were not taught practically in the laboratory; they were not exposed to computer/ICT devices. The problems of computer/ICT implementation mainly have to do with finance, man power and infrastructure.

Importance of Laboratory to Science Teaching

Laboratory is one of the important aspects in teaching and learning of science. Therefore, Anderson (1976) defines a laboratory as “a place where a person or group of persons engage in human enterprises of examining and explaining natural phenomena”. Laboratories, however, were usually not associated with educational institution before the eighteenth century. Lilley (1951) pointed out that there were no scientific instruments designed for the study of science in the main before 1600. The inclusion of laboratory facilities as part of science teaching therefore was first established by Liesery (1803) as reported by Rosen and Michelle (1995). The present class then, performs experiment, thereby gaining not only a knowledge of elements of their most useful components but also by the success and failure of their experiment, they receive education in patience, watchfulness, and exercise of fore thought that will prove invaluable by them through life, on the discharge of domestic, social and professional duties.

Quality and Qualification of Teacher

Computer education can be explained through the attitude and behaviors of their teachers. Teachers' behavior is a critical influence on students' confidence and attitude towards Computer study as they provide important role model to their students (Derbyshire, 2003). Lack of adequate training and experience is one of the main reasons why teachers do not use technology in their teaching. This also eventuates in teachers' negative attitude towards computer and technology. In addition, lack of confidence leads to reluctance to use computers by the teachers (Kumar & Kumar, 2003). Attitude of pre-service and in-service teachers towards computer and technology skills can be improved by integrating technology into teacher education (Zammit, 1992). Findings shown that a significant relationship exist between computer attitude and its use in institutions for pre-service teachers (Khine, 2001), and also for serving teachers in the affective attitude, general usefulness, behavioral control, and pedagogical use (Yuen & Ma, 2001).

Computer teachers are usually required to obtain Bachelor's or graduate degree in Computer Science Education or minimum qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) (NPE, 2013). Computer education competencies required by teachers were highlighted by

Kirschner and Woperies (2003) to include: Competency in making personal use of Computer; Mastery of a range of educational paradigms that make use of Computer; Competency in making use of ICT as minds tools; Competency in using Computer knowledge as a tool for teaching; and competency in mastering a range of assessment paradigms which involves use of Computer; Competency in understanding the policy dimensions of the use of Computer for teaching and learning. Pre-service teacher education should focus on the need for student-teachers to have Computer skills for their own use in the preparation of materials for teaching and learning activities; the need to facilitate the direct use of ICT in students' learning activities within the classroom situation; and the need for teachers to develop in their students a critical awareness of Computer applications and the social implications (Robbins, 1998).

Benefit/Importance of Computer Education

Computer education has become one of the vital tools necessary for promoting education worldwide, through the use of computers and internet facilities, information are sourced, disseminated and also stored. The internet can be used to teach and learn, search for information that is within the educational circle. The study of computer education in Nigerian

schools tends to determine what impact it has in training the students in automobile trade at the secondary school or college level. The use of computer has become the most popularized means of facilitating teaching and learning in the recent time in this 21st century (Ayelaygbe, 2005). Chamberlain (2013) explained that Computer usage has turned out to be the fastest means of passing information to every educational sector.

According to Onyemezi (2002) for an enhanced teaching and learning of computer science, the method of teaching should not be by theoretical aspect alone, rather it should be by practical demonstration; this is to mean that computer system is very much important hence its subject is learned in real presentation of theory. Since computer science is underlined to be a prevocational subject, in order to achieve the underlined objective of the junior secondary school, it is planned to be vocational and academic by National Policy on Education. As such the use of laboratory facilities with functional computer systems becomes necessary.

Dawson (1997) noted that, computer influenced many fields of human endeavor including education. He stressed that if students are to be prepared for job after school, they must be acquainted with computer application in

information processing because computer has shifted learning from the traditional textbook to system where student uses it for real life problems.

According to Eya (2000) computer plays an important role in educational system. He said it is a science that made the study of the world easy since it transforms teaching from theory to practice. Considering some major objectives of the Universal Basic Education in junior secondary schools, the acquisition of appropriate skills or level of literacy, numeric, manipulative, communication and problem-solving skills will require computer science and literacy.

The National Policy on Education (2004), in considering the objectives of computer science as a prevocational subject, recommended practical use of teaching. In pursuit of realising the policy, there has been an increasing demand for scientists, technologists and technicians in the industrial sector. Computer science is a basic science subject which is very necessary in the study of all the science subjects in the 21st century and beyond. Computer as such needs a good Instructional facilitator to help the student develop positive attitudes towards science. According to Akusoba (1999) the basic objective of teaching computer is to develop in the students the desired practical skill and

habits such as observation, reflective thinking and problem solving.

Problem Facing Teaching of Computer Studies in Secondary Schools

Computer education refers to the amount of knowledge and skills acquired by an individual to perform a given task using a computer system. Expectedly, the knowledge and skills acquired in this area may be very high, low or very low, depending on the individual's exposure to computer facilities. Computer education is of paramount importance to national development and it is on this premise that the government of Nigeria sought to introduce computer studies in the educational system from primary through to tertiary institutions. (Wikipedia, 2017)

According to Yusuf (2005), problems of teaching computer in secondary school includes; firstly, Equity issues: that many people view computer science as gender base. They believe that computer are made for men not women. Secondly, Technological Issues: It is a challenge that occurs where the school lacks teaching aids such as computer, projector, gadget, power supply, etc. Thirdly, Socio-economic Issues: this means that people from wealthy family use computer more than the people from poor background, so because of this, the rich children know or understand computer. Fourthly, Societal Issues: the

society or environment where student found themselves contributes to their level of understanding. It is easy to teach computer at the urban area than rural area because the people in urban area use computer more than those at the rural area. And lastly, pedagogical Issues: many teachers lack mastery of the subject matters and at the same time.

Despite the importance of computer in our education system and nation in general, many facts however have hindered the growth and adoption of computer science in Nigeria secondary school. Such factor ranges from lack of interest in computer studies on the part of the student to lack of dedication on the part of the teacher. Kwaches (2007) remarked that most school lack computer literate teachers and experts that would support and manage the application of computing in teaching and learning processes. The need to solve the problem of dearth of computer literate teachers might not be unconnected with the inclusion of ICT in teaching training programmer in schools. So for effective teaching and learning to take place, there must be well qualified and competent teacher who will handle and teach the students effectively. ICTs have a significant impact on all areas of human activity (Brakel and Chisenga, 2003).

Practical work constitutes an integral part of science teaching, yet

students are being denied exposure to sufficient practical in schools. In most of our secondary schools, science teachings have become verbal affairs. Some teachers spend much time in explanation, finalizing the teaching through verbal means. Such teachers deny students the vital opportunity to learn things themselves.

Green (2000), emphasized that practice work must be practical process in which the pupil at very stage actively participates instead of being purely a passive receiver of verbal instruction. Willey (2010), maintained that if students are really to understand the nature of scientific process active participation on that process is required.

Statement of the Problem

Computer has taken over the world activities such as business, education, research, medicine, etc. Its importance cannot be over emphasized. However, considering that students were taught computer in their various schools but most of them could not identify computer physically raises the question as to the quality of instruction in the subject. How effective is the teaching of computer science in our schools and what is the quality and qualification of computer science teachers in Nigeria and Sokoto in particular? This study intends to assess the availabilities of computer laboratories

and teachers' qualification in Secondary School in Sokoto South Local Government Area.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to assess the teacher's qualification as well as the laboratory facilities for effective teaching and learning of computer studies in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area. The study in particularly tends to investigate the following,

1. Assess the level of the computer teachers' qualification in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area.
2. Examine the ratio of teacher to students in computer laboratory.
3. Determine the availability of computer laboratory facilities in Junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following are research questions;

1. What is the level of computer studies teacher's qualification in Secondary School in Sokoto South Local Government Area?
2. What is the ratio of teacher to students in computer laboratory?
3. To what extent are computer laboratory facilities available in Secondary Schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area?

Research Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey design. According to Anaekwe & Ozigbo (2002), Descriptive research design is connected with the collection of data for the purpose of describing and interpreting existing conditions. The population of this study consists of all Public Secondary School offering computer studies as subject in Sokoto South Local Government Area. There are nineteen (19) secondary schools in Sokoto South LGA but not all are offering computer studies as a subject. However, in order to find out the teacher's qualification and all computer teachers in the selected schools were considered. Ten (10) governments Junior Secondary School in Sokoto South Local Government Area were selected using purposive sampling techniques; this is because not all the schools have the required qualification for the selection in this study, which is the offer of computer studies as a result as a subject studied. Four (4) girls school and Six (6) mixed secondary school (boys and girls) were randomly selected. More so, all the computer teachers in the sample schools were considered. The instrument was examined by two experts in the Science Education Department, and based on their correction, some items on the checklist were removed. The instrument was modified for the purpose of this

research. In order to test the reliability of this instrument, a pilot study was conducted in some schools outside the study area. The result obtained was used to calculate the reliability of the instrument using Cronbach's alpha. The reliability was found to be 0.78, thereby making the instrument reliable for the study. The researcher personally administered the checklist to the computer teachers for part A and it was filled as indicated in the instruction, while the researchers scored the other parts B & C based on their observation. The entire checklist was collected and the data collected, were analysed using Statistic Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results

The data obtained from the field of the study was presented and analyzed with the aim of answering the stated questions through the use of the tables as follows:

Table 4.1.1: Showing Teachers' Qualification in Secondary School in Sokoto South Local Government Area?

S/N	Items	No.	Frequency	Percentage
1	B.Sc. Ed.	10	8	15.10%
2	B.Sc.	10	11	20.75%
3	HND	10	14	26.42%
4	NCE	10	15	28.30%
5	OND	10	5	9.43%
	Total		53	100%

Source: Primary Education Board

The table 4.1.1 above shows the qualification of the teachers obtained in this study. 8 teachers which represent 15.10% of the population hold a B.Sc. Ed. 11 teachers which represents 20.75% of the population hold a holding B.Sc. 14 or 26.42% of the population have HND. 15 teachers representing 28.30% of the population are NCE graduates. Last but not the least, 5 teachers which represents 9.43% of the population are OND qualification.

Table 4.1.2: Showing Ratio of Teachers to Students in computer laboratory

Schools	Ratio of Teacher to Students
A	4:1166
B	6:2085
C	3:875
D	3:590
E	8:890
F	9:1020
G	3:1085
H	5:80
I	3:184
J	9:1065
Total	53:9040

Source: Primary Education Board

Note: A – J represent schools

The table 4.1.2 above shows the ratio of teacher in the sample schools. The result shows that there is an average of about 1:170 teacher – student ratio in the 10 schools studied. In school A, for example there are 4 teachers to 1166 students; school B has 6 teachers to 2085; school C has 3 teachers to 875 students; in school D, 3 teachers to 590 students; 8 teachers

to 890 students in school E; 9 teachers to 1020 students in school F; 3:1085 in school G; 5:80 in school H; 8 teachers to 184 students in school I, and 9 teachers to 1065 students in school J.

Table 4.1.3: Showing Summary and Result of the Respondent on the extent to which computer laboratory facilities are available in Secondary Schools in Sokoto South LGA

S/N	Items	No.	HA	MA	LA	NA
1	Computer	10	4(40%)	3(30%)	3(30%)	0(0%)
2	Projector	10	1(10%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	9(90%)
3	Printer	10	2(20%)	3(30%)	5(50%)	0(0%)
4	Scanner	10	0(0%)	2(20%)	4(40%)	4(40%)
5	Photocopier	10	0(0%)	4(40%)	5(50)	1(10%)
6	Internet	10	0(0%)	1(10%)	1(10%)	8(80%)
7	Power	10	0(0%)	9(90%)	1(10%)	0(0%)
8	Educational Applications	10	1(10%)	9(90%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
9	Interactive Board	10	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	10(100%)
10	External Drives	10	3(30%)	2(20%)	5(50%)	0(0%)

Source: Research Fieldwork

The table 4.1.3 shows that 4 out of 10 school representing 40% computers are highly available, while in 3 out of 10 schools representing 30% they are moderately available, while in another 3 out of 10 schools representing 30% the availability of computer is low. On item 2, it shows that only 1 out of 10 schools representing 10% have available projector, while in 9 out of 10 schools representing 90% projector are not available. On item 3, it shows that there is 2 out of 10 schools representing 20%

have high availability of printers, while 3 out of 10 schools representing 30% has moderate availability and 5 out of 10 schools representing 50% has low availability of printers. Also on item 4, it shows that 2 out of 10 school representing 20% has moderate availability of scanners, while 4 out of 10 schools representing 40% has low availability, while 4 out of 10 schools representing 40% has no scanner. On item 5, the data obtained shows that 4 out of 10 school representing 40% has moderate availability of photocopier, while 5 out of 10 schools representing 50% has low availability, and 1 out of 10 schools representing 10% has no photocopier. On item 6 result indicate that 1 out of 10 schools representing 10% has moderate availability of internet, while 1 out of 10 schools representing 10% has low internet, and 8 out of 10 schools representing 80% has no internet. On item 7, it shows that 9 out of 10 schools representing 90% has moderate available of power, while 1 out of 10 has low available power. Also, item 8 shows that 1 out of 10 schools representing 10% has high available educational applications, while 9 out 10 schools representing 90% has moderate available educational applications. On item 9, it shows that 10 out of 10 schools representing 100% has no interactive board. Lastly, on item 10, it shows that

there is a high availability of external drive in 3 out of 10 schools representing 30%, while 2 out of 10 schools representing 20% has moderate available external drives, and 5 out of 10 schools representing 50% has low available external drives.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this research shows that majority of the computer teachers in junior secondary schools are not qualified. Data collected indicated that 56.6% of the computer teachers are not qualified while 43.3% are qualified. The findings of this studies assent to the finding of Ifejika (1990) that most teachers teaching computer are not qualified. He concluded that the teaching of science and technical subject such as computer requires the use of specialist and qualified teachers so as to expose the students to the content of the subject matter effectively. Yusuf (2005) also affirmed that one of the problems of teaching computer in junior secondary school is that most of the teachers are unqualified, they have little knowledge of subject matter and also apply method that are not suitable.

Moreover, this research shows that there are not enough teachers to teach computer in junior secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government, Sokoto State. This finding

does not assent to the standard provided by the National Policy on Education therefore; the ratio of teacher to student is very low.

This research also found out that laboratory facilities are highly available for teaching and learning of computer in junior secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area, Sokoto State which is contrary to the finding of Alebiosu (2000) and Onipede (2003) which had concluded in their studies that many schools do not have required laboratory facilities.

Summary of the Major Findings

Based on the research and discussion so far, the following findings were made:

1. The ratio of teacher to students is very low compared to NPE standard which says 50 students per teacher.
2. There are unqualified computer studies teachers across junior secondary schools in Sokoto South local government area of Sokoto State.
3. The number of working computers is high in most of the schools laboratory.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the availability of qualified teachers and laboratory facilities for effective teaching and learning of

computer science in junior secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area of Sokoto State.

To do this effectively, a number of research questions were formulated, review of related literature was carried out to highlight other people's views on the topic. A total of 10 schools were sampled in the selected schools. The data collected were analyzed and presented in tables using simple percentage. Based on the analyses some findings were made and presented.

Based on the finding of this research, the following conclusions are drawn.

1. Computer teachers in junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto South are unqualified therefore cripples effective teaching of computer in junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto South, Sokoto State.
2. The student to teacher ratio is very high compared to the requirement outlined by the National Policy on Education.
3. There are enough laboratory facilities that will elevate effective teaching of computer in junior Secondary Schools in Sokoto South local Government Sokoto State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research study the following recommendations are made:

1. The Government should employ and post enough qualified teachers in computer studies to different junior secondary school, especially in Sokoto South Local Government Area.
2. The Federal Ministry of Education and the State Education Commission should occasionally organize workshop, refresher courses for qualified teachers and in service training for unqualified teachers on the use and manipulation of science laboratory equipment.
3. Professional bodies should organize workshop, seminar, training and other courses that will ensure computer teachers competence and increase their knowledge of subject matter.

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